

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF DEGREE OF ADJECTIVE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

This article examines the parallels and differences in the degree of adjectives in English and Uzbek languages. Adjectives are crucial linguistic tools for conveying attributes and making comparisons in both languages. While both English and Uzbek use inflectional methods to indicate positive, comparative, and superlative degrees, they follow different patterns and usage standards. In English, comparative and superlative degrees are frequently produced with suffixes or auxiliary words, but Uzbek use suffixes and unique auxiliary words. Despite these changes, adjectives' essential role in refining descriptions and communicating subtle meanings is identical throughout both languages.

This comparative research offers insight on the complex interplay between linguistic structures and cultural settings, emphasizing the dynamic aspect of language change. Examining the degree of adjectives in English and Uzbek provides useful insights into language variation as well as how languages create and reflect cultural norms and values. Understanding these parallels and contrasts not only enhances our appreciation for language complexity, but it also promotes crosscultural understanding and communication.

Keywords: *Adjectives, degree of comparison, English language, Uzbek language, comparative analysis, linguistic diversity.*

Adjectives play a crucial role in both English and Uzbek languages, enriching descriptions and adding depth to communication. One fascinating aspect of adjectives is how they express degrees of comparison, conveying qualities such as superiority, equality, or inferiority. In this article, we will explore the similarities and differences in the degree of adjectives between English and Uzbek languages, shedding light on their respective structures and usage.

Degree of adjectives in English:

Adjective degree is a fundamental component of English grammar that enables speakers and writers to describe nouns with varied degrees of intensity or comparison. Adjectives modify nouns by adding information about their attributes,

which can be expressed in three different ways: **positive, comparative, and superlative**. **1. Positive Degree:** The positive degree is the most basic form of the adjective, used to describe a noun without drawing a comparison. It is used to express the existence of a quality without comparing it to anything else. Adjectives in the positive degree include: *big, little, tall, joyful, sorrowful, and beautiful*.

2. Comparative Degree: The comparative degree is used to compare two things or two sets of traits. Adjectives of the comparative degree often terminate in *"-er"* or are preceded by *"more."* - When generating the comparative degree, adjectives with one or two syllables often take *the "-er" suffix*, whereas lengthier adjectives *take "more."* - Adjectives in the comparative degree include : *larger, smaller, taller, happier, sadder, and more attractive*.

3. Superlative Degree: The superlative degree is employed when comparing three or more objects or to describe the highest level of a quality. - Adjectives in the superlative degree usually finish in *"-est"* or are preceded by *"most."* - When generating the superlative degree, adjectives with one or two syllables typically take *the "-est" suffix*, whereas lengthier adjectives *take "most."* - Adjectives in the superlative degree include : *biggest, smallest, tallest, happiest, saddest, and most beautiful*.

Degree of adjectives in Uzbek:

Adjectives in Uzbek can be inflected to indicate three levels of comparison: **positive, comparative, and superlative**.

1. Positive degree: This is the adjectives base form, which is used to characterize a noun without drawing comparisons.

For instance: Yaxshi (good). katta (large) ko'p (many).

2. Comparative degree: This adjective is used to compare two items or individuals. In Uzbek, the comparative degree is constructed by adding the *suffix "roq"* to the positive form of an adjective. *For example: yaxshiroq (better). kattaroq (larger) ko'proq (more)*

3. Superlative degree: This adjective is employed when comparing three or more things or individuals. In Uzbek, the superlative degree is constructed by adding the *suffix "chi"* to the positive form of an adjective. *For example: - eng yaxshi (the best) - eng katta (the biggest) - eng ko'p (the most)* It's important to note that some adjectives in Uzbek have irregular forms in the comparative and superlative degrees, so it's best to consult a dictionary or reference guide for specific examples. Overall, understanding and using the three degrees of comparison in Uzbek adjectives can help you effectively describe and compare different qualities or characteristics in the language.

Similarities and Differences:

Both English and Uzbek utilize adjectives to describe nouns and convey degrees of comparison, although their methods differ slightly.

Similarities is Basic Function: Adjectives in both languages modify nouns to provide descriptive information.

Degrees of Comparison: Both languages express degrees of comparison, but English uses a formal system with suffixes while Uzbek relies on adverbs and comparison words.

Differences is Formal System: English employs a formal system for forming comparative and superlative degrees, while Uzbek lacks such a system and relies more on word order and adverbs. **Suffixes:** English often uses suffixes (*-er/-est*) or the words "*more*" and "*most*" to form degrees, whereas Uzbek uses adverbs and comparison words more frequently. **Structure:** English adjectives typically precede the noun they modify, whereas Uzbek allows for more flexibility in word order.

In conclusion, in English, adjective degree is formally structured into **positive**, **comparative**, and **superlative forms**, often achieved through suffixes or the use of "*more*" and "*most*." Adjectives generally precede the noun they modify, and there are strict rules governing their usage and placement.

On the other hand, Uzbek lacks a formal system of adjective degree, relying more on word order, adverbs, and comparison words to convey degrees of comparison. Adjectives in Uzbek can appear both before and after the noun they modify, offering more flexibility in sentence construction. While both languages serve the same basic function of describing nouns and conveying degrees of comparison, they differ in their formal systems, methods of expression, and structural rules. Understanding these distinctions is essential for learners to effectively navigate and use adjectives in both English and Uzbek.

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